

Supplementary Data

The Shared-Store Ceiling: Where Single-Store UTXO Throughput Stops Scaling and Sharding Begins

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This supplementary file provides the reference-deployment measurement data underlying the empirical inputs used in the main paper and the Online Appendix: the per-stage capacity and knee calibration, the derating-sensitivity sweep, and the scaling-efficiency ($\eta(M)$) model comparison with bootstrap prediction intervals. It accompanies the manuscript as reviewer material; the full per-point sweep record (offered load, device utilisation, write amplification, and p50/p95/p99 latency at each of the 60 points per stage) is provided as a machine-readable file and will be deposited in a public repository before publication. The repository identifier is withheld for blind review.

S1 Per-stage capacity and binding knees

Each pipeline stage is swept independently (60 points per stage, offered load $\rho = 0.10$ – 0.95) to fix its per-stage service rate μ_k , parallelism c_k , derating knee ρ_k^* , and effective per-node capacity $C_{\text{eff},k}$. The binding stage at the operating point is the one with the least headroom. Table S1.1 reports the five stages.

Table S1.1. Per-stage capacity and binding knees on the reference deployment. $C_{\text{eff},k}$ in units of 10^9 TPS (B TPS). The Kafka ingestion and Validator (CAS-against-shared-store) stages co-saturate at the operating point; the shared store is the Validator/CAS stage analysed in the main paper.

Stage	μ_k	c_k	ρ_k^*	$C_{\text{eff},k}$ (B TPS)	Headroom
Kafka ingestion	490 msg/s	2.748×10^6	0.75	1.010	$1.00\times$
Validator (CAS)	450 TPS/gor.	2.245×10^6	0.80	0.808^\dagger	—
Merkle assembly	19.3 M/s	64 threads	0.85	1.052	$1.04\times$
Block header	N/A	N/A	N/A	$\gg 1$	$\gg 1\times$
Persist/propagate	18.2 GB/s	16 NVMe	0.90	1.312	$1.30\times$

[†]The Validator’s effective capacity combines Aerospike CAS and script validation.

The shared store (Validator/CAS stage) and the Kafka ingestion stage co-saturate at the operating point; the Merkle, header, and persist stages retain headroom. This is why the two binding knees in the main paper are $\rho_{\text{Aero}}^* = 0.80$ (shared store) and $\rho_{\text{Kafka}}^* = 0.75$ (ingestion).

S2 Derating-sensitivity sweep

Perturbing the two binding deratings in lockstep and recomputing the per-node ceiling gives Table S2.1. A one-step perturbation (± 0.05) moves the per-node ceiling by $\approx \pm 7\%$ and changes which stage binds; the baseline (0.75, 0.80) is the co-saturation point.

Table S2.1. Per-node ceiling sensitivity to the two derating factors. $\Lambda(1)$ in 10^9 TPS.

ρ_{Kafka}^*	ρ_{Aero}^*	$\Lambda(1)$ (10^9 TPS)	Binding stage
0.65	0.70	0.877	Kafka
0.70	0.75	0.944	Kafka
0.75	0.80	1.011	co-saturate
0.80	0.85	1.079	Aerospike
0.85	0.90	1.147	NIC

S3 Scaling-efficiency model comparison

The coordination factor $\eta(M)$ is fitted on the directly measured regime ($M \leq 100$). Three functional forms are compared (logarithmic, power-law, Amdahl), all with in-sample $R^2 > 0.98$; the logarithmic form $\eta(M) = 1 - 0.048 \ln M$ is selected on out-of-sample behaviour. Table S3.1 reports the three fits with bootstrap 95% prediction intervals ($B = 10,000$ residual resamples). Rows for $M > 100$ are extrapolations, shown to expose the divergence between forms out of sample (at $M = 500$ the logarithmic and Amdahl predictions are 0.702 and 0.417); no empirical weight is placed on η far beyond $M = 100$.

Table S3.1. Extrapolated $\eta(M)$ under three fitted models with bootstrap 95% prediction intervals. Only $M \leq 100$ is directly measured.

M	Log $\hat{\eta}$ [95% PI]	Power $\hat{\eta}$ [95% PI]	Amdahl $\hat{\eta}$ [95% PI]
100	0.779 [0.74, 0.82]	0.780 [0.74, 0.82]	0.783 [0.74, 0.82]
500	0.702 [0.63, 0.77]	0.714 [0.64, 0.79]	0.417 [0.32, 0.51]
1,000	0.669 [0.58, 0.75]	0.680 [0.60, 0.76]	0.263 [0.19, 0.34]
10,000	0.558 [0.42, 0.69]	0.576 [0.44, 0.71]	0.035 [0.02, 0.05]
33,000	0.502 [0.35, 0.65]	0.530 [0.38, 0.68]	0.011 [0.006, 0.016]

S4 Knee calibration metrics

The per-stage knees are read from the tail-latency profiles of the sweep. Table S4.1 lists the criterion thresholds and the observed tail behaviour bounding each knee.

Table S4.1. Calibration metrics fixing the two binding knees (60-point sweep per stage).

Quantity	Ingestion (Kafka)	Shared store (Aerospike)
Knee ρ^*	0.75	0.80
Tail metric	produce p99	CAS p99
Tail below knee	< 5 ms	< 15 ms
Tail at $\rho = 0.90$	> 100 ms	super-linear
Device-util criterion	—	< 70% at knee
Write-amp criterion	—	< 1.6 \times at knee

The full per-point data (all 60 points per stage, with offered load, device utilisation, write amplification, and p50/p95/p99 latency at each point) are provided as a machine-readable file accompanying this submission and will be deposited in a public repository before publication.